

Client-Side Verifiable Presentation System with Passkey-Derived Persistent Keys and Pairwise Service Bindings

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Abstract. This paper describes a client-side system for creating Verifiable Presentations (VPs) entirely within a web browser, without server round-trips during presentation generation. The system employs two key derivation strategies: (A) a passkey-derived strategy using the WebAuthn PRF (Pseudo-Random Function) extension to derive deterministic cryptographic keys from a passkey, enabling the same keys to be available on any device where the passkey is synced, and (B) a device-bound strategy using non-extractable Web Crypto API keys with OPAQUE session key-based wrapping for cross-device recovery. Both strategies produce pairwise per-service binding identifiers, preventing cross-service profile linkage. VP creation operates offline (~ 50 ms with biometric cache) using locally cached encrypted profile blobs and per-service X.509 binding certificates. The system includes automatic certificate renewal, authenticator change detection, and selective disclosure of profile claims within the VP payload.

Keywords: verifiable presentations · WebAuthn · passkey · PRF extension · key derivation · pairwise identifiers · OPAQUE · offline credentials

1 Background and Problem Statement

1.1 The Server-Dependent VP Problem

Existing Verifiable Credential (VC) and Verifiable Presentation (VP) systems typically require either: (a) a server-side signing operation for each presentation, introducing latency and a single point of failure, or (b) export of private keys to the client device, creating key management and revocation challenges.

The W3C Verifiable Credentials Data Model (v2.0) defines the holder role but does not specify how a holder's signing keys are derived, stored, or synchronized across devices. In practice, most implementations delegate signing to a cloud wallet or require device-specific key provisioning.

1.2 The Cross-Device Key Synchronization Problem

Users access identity services from multiple devices. Private keys used for VP signing must be available on all devices without explicit key transfer ceremonies. Traditional approaches (QR-code pairing, cloud key escrow, hardware token) add friction or security trade-offs.

The WebAuthn PRF extension (W3C Web Authentication Level 3) provides a mechanism for deriving deterministic pseudo-random values from passkey authentication. Since passkeys are synchronizable across devices via platform credential managers (iCloud Keychain, Google Password Manager), a PRF-derived key is automatically available on any device where the passkey is synced—without explicit key synchronization.

1.3 The Linkability Problem

When a user presents credentials to multiple relying parties, using the same identifier or signing key across services enables cross-service tracking. Pairwise pseudonymous identifiers (OIDC PPID) address this at the identifier level, but the signing key itself can serve as a correlator if the same public key appears in VPs to different services.

2 System Architecture

2.1 Strategy Selection

The system operates in one of two strategies, automatically selected based on browser capabilities:

- **Strategy A (Passkey-Derived):** Used when the browser supports the WebAuthn PRF extension. Deterministic keys derived from passkey PRF output. Cross-device sync via passkey sync.
- **Strategy B (Device-Bound):** Fallback when PRF is unavailable. Non-extractable keys generated per-device via Web Crypto API. Cross-device recovery via OPAQUE session export key wrapping.

2.2 Component Overview

The system comprises four components, all executing within the browser:

1. **Key Derivation Module:** Derives or generates signing keys (ECDSA P-256) and data encryption keys (AES-256-GCM).
2. **Profile Cache:** Stores the user’s encrypted profile blob in IndexedDB. The server never holds the decryption key.
3. **Binding Manager:** Maintains per-service binding entries (pairwise ID, HD index, X.509 cert, expiry).
4. **VP Builder:** Constructs and signs VPs from cached data using the signing key and binding certificate.

3 Strategy A: Passkey-Derived Keys (PRF)

3.1 PRF Evaluation

During passkey authentication, the system requests evaluation of the WebAuthn PRF extension with a fixed application-specific label:

```
prfInput = { eval: { first: encode("sid-ppk-v1") } }
```

The PRF output is a 32-byte pseudo-random value determined by the passkey's internal secret and the input label. The same passkey with the same label produces the same output on any device.

3.2 Key Derivation Chain

The PRF output serves as entropy for HKDF-SHA256:

```
baseKey = HKDF.importKey(prfOutput)
signingBits = HKDF.deriveBits(baseKey,
    salt="sid-ppk-v1", info="signing-key", 256)
dataBits = HKDF.deriveBits(baseKey,
    salt="sid-ppk-v1", info="data-encryption-key", 256)
```

- `signingBits` → ECDSA P-256 private key (deterministic from seed)
- `dataBits` → AES-256-GCM key (imported directly)

Both keys are deterministic: same passkey on any device → same signing key → same verifiable identity.

3.3 Authenticator Change Detection

If the user replaces their passkey, the PRF output changes. Detection:

```
currentHash = SHA-256(exportPublicKey(signingKey))
```

If `currentHash` \neq `storedHash`: trigger re-enrollment (re-encrypt profile, re-issue certificates, update hash).

4 Strategy B: Device-Bound Keys

4.1 Key Generation

When PRF is unavailable:

```
signingKeyPair = crypto.subtle.generateKey(
    ECDSA P-256, non-extractable)
dataKey = crypto.subtle.generateKey(
    AES-256-GCM, non-extractable)
```

4.2 Cross-Device Recovery via OPAQUE Session Key

The signing key is wrapped using a key derived from the OPAQUE [4] session export key:

```
wrappingKey = HKDF(opaqueSessionExportKey,
    salt="sid-device-key-wrap",
    info="wrapping-key")
wrappedKey = AES-KW.wrap(signingKey, wrappingKey)
```

The server stores the wrapped key but cannot unwrap it (the OPAQUE session export key is derived from the user's password, which the server never sees).

5 Pairwise Service Bindings

5.1 Binding Identifier Generation

For each (profile, service sector) pair, a unique binding identifier is generated. Different services see different identifiers—no cross-service linkage.

Each binding entry: bindingId (opaque UUID), bindingIndex (HD derivation), certChain (per-binding X.509), certExpiry, lastUsedAt.

5.2 Service Sector Determination

Derived from: `sector_identifier_uri` host > redirect URI host > site domain. Same sector = same binding (intra-org SSO). Different sectors = always different bindings.

5.3 Certificate Lifecycle

- **Issuance:** Lazy—first VP request triggers online issuance
- **Caching:** IndexedDB alongside binding entry
- **Renewal:** Background, 7 days before expiry
- **Enforcement:** VP creation blocked if certificate expired

6 VP Creation (Offline)

6.1 Flow

1. Relying party sends: {nonce, requestedClaims, audience, serviceSector}
2. Load binding entry from IndexedDB
3. Verify certificate not expired
4. Build payload: nonce, audience, bindingId, claims, timestamp
5. Sign with ECDSA P-256 SHA-256
6. Return VP: {payload, signature, certChain, nonce, audience}

Entirely offline. Typical latency: ~50 ms.

6.2 Selective Disclosure

Only requested claims included in VP payload. Profile blob decrypted locally; unrequested claims never leave the browser.

7 Security Properties

- **Key Confidentiality:** Strategy A: PRF output never leaves authenticator hardware. Strategy B: non-extractable keys (Web Crypto enforcement).
- **Unlinkability:** Different service sectors → different binding IDs and optionally different public keys.
- **Replay Protection:** Per-VP nonce and timestamp verified by relying party.
- **Revocation:** Per-binding certificates revocable via CRL/OCSP by identity provider.

8 Novelty Claims

1. **Passkey PRF as persistent key derivation source**—using WebAuthn PRF to derive deterministic signing and encryption keys, enabling cross-device availability via passkey sync
2. **Dual-strategy key management (PRF + device-bound)**—automatic fallback with OPAQUE-wrapped cross-device recovery
3. **Offline VP creation from encrypted local cache**—complete VP construction (~50ms) without server round-trip
4. **Per-service pairwise binding with lazy certificate issuance**—unique (profile, sector) binding with on-demand X.509 issuance and background renewal
5. **Authenticator change detection via public key hash**—passkey replacement detected by comparing derived key hash, triggering automatic re-enrollment
6. **OPAQUE session export key as device recovery mechanism**—wrapping device keys with password-derived (server-invisible) key for cross-device transfer

Defensive Publication Statement

This document is published as a defensive disclosure to establish prior art for the described techniques. The disclosure is made by Dmitry Prudnikov to prevent third parties from obtaining patent rights that would restrict the use of these techniques.

The described system is implemented as part of the StructuredID identity provider platform (<https://structured.id>), published under the GNU Affero General Public License 3.0 (AGPL-3.0) for the Community Edition.

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